

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Factors motivating head teachers in Marakwet west Sub County to enroll for the KEMI diploma in educational management course

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Abstract

Head teachers of primary schools have to deal with a lot of shifting managerial environments, which sometimes makes them ineffective in their expanding responsibilities. Therefore, providing targeted in-service training has never been essential. Head teachers in Kenya's Marakwet West Sub County were asked to participate in the KEMI Diploma in Educational Management Course as part of this study. The research design was a descriptive survey. The sample consisted of 38 head teachers chosen through stratified random sampling from 57 schools whose heads had completed the KEMI Diploma in Education Management, 42 teachers chosen at random, and 13 chairpersons of the Board of Management chosen intentionally from the same schools. Data was gathered through the use of questionnaires. The information was summed up and introduced utilizing recurrence tables, charts and rates. The study found that head teachers were motivated by the need to improve their skills, a raise in pay, and a higher job grade. In order to encourage teachers to participate in useful professional development programs, the study suggested that head teachers' job evaluations include an audit of skill requirements, continuous short-term refresher courses in areas that were studied, decentralization of training, and recognition of head teachers' academic achievement through promotion and salary increments. The study found that there were gaps between the course content and the actual management skills that school managers need, such as ICT skills and financial management bookkeeping. The TSC's selection, promotion, and deployment of head teachers of primary schools should also be reviewed, according to the study.

Keywords: Factors; Head teachers; Diploma; Management

1. Introduction

The issue of insufficient school initiative has been of incredible worry to strategy creators. In light of the government's plan to improve schools through education reforms and the rise in primary school enrollment as a result of Free Primary Education (FPE) in 2003, school administrators need to be well-informed right away. The Kenya Education Staff Institute (KESI) was probably established by the Government of Kenya (GoK) in 1981 as a means of developing managerial staff at the Ministry of Education, including head teachers of all schools. KESI expanded its mandate for enhancing education capacity to address the issue of ineffective school managers. As a result, the name of the organization was changed from KESI to Kenya Education Management Institute (KEMI) in 2011, as stated in (1). KEMI assesses the requirements for in-service training and staff development by collaborating with various education subsectors. KEMI is in charge of coordinating the creation and distribution of educational materials for educational professionals and administrators.

Head teachers' difficulties managing schools are linked, according to a number of studies, to a lack of ongoing skill development through training. As a result, head teachers appear to prioritize administrative and financial concerns over curriculum delivery, monitoring, and evaluation supervision (2). 3) Observed that a lot of teachers were uneasy around head teachers who lacked the necessary school management skills. According to a study conducted in Busia and Teso

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District to determine the impact of the PRISM in-service program, schools led by PRISM-trained head teachers performed slightly better on KCPE tests than schools led by head teachers who were not in-serviced (3). Different examinations demonstrated that some of the Crystal prepared heads had since resigned or were as of now not in that frame of mind in elementary schools. For instance, a baseline survey that was carried out in the Sengwer zone of the Marakwet West District found that more than 15 head teachers who had been trained under the PRISM in-service were no longer in positions of authority. This suggested that the Teachers' Service Commission, a government agency that is in charge of promoting teachers and sending them to primary schools, does not rely on education management training. Primary schools are run poorly and ineffectively by school teachers who do not have any management experience at all.

KEMI had only conducted a need assessment for secondary school principals, according to observation from (4). It was noted that primary school principals did not receive the same training, despite taking a similar education management course. Due to differences in organization, scope, and environmental conditions, the management and leadership needs of the two levels of school management may differ. The specific goal of the study was to determine the factors that significantly influenced Marakwet West Sub County head teachers to enroll in the KEMI Diploma in Educational Management Course.

2. Material and methods

The research was descriptive in nature. The study's focus was on 57 public primary schools in Marakwet West Sub County whose principals had completed the KEMI diploma in Education Management program. The subcounty of Marakwet West was broken up into seven educational zones; each with distinctive features. The Arid zone, for instance, could be classified as Arid and Semi-Arid Land (ASAL). The remaining six zones had a reasonable amount of economic potential. There were 93 respondents, which included 38 head teachers, 42 teachers, and 13 chairpersons of the school board of management.

38 head teachers were chosen using proportionate sampling from each of the seven educational zones. The BoM's 42 teachers and 13 chairpersons were selected using simple random sampling, which ensured that each member of the defined population had an equal and independent chance of being included in the sample.

The questionnaires and interview schedules used in the study were used to collect data. Due to their literacy, questionnaires were developed for teachers and head teachers. The schedules of interviews were used to collect data from the BoM chairpersons.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 Motivating Factors for Enrolment in the KEMI Diploma

Motivating Factor		Degree of Motivation					Statistic	
		Very Low	Low	High	Very High	Total Valid	Mean	Std. Dev.
Government Sponsorship	Frequency	2	3	8	25	38		
	%Valid	5.3	7.9	21.1	65.8	100.0	3.47	.86
Convenient Mode of Study	Frequency	1	5	16	16	38		
	% Valid	2.6	13.2	42.1	42.1	100.0	3.24	.79
Promotion/ Grade	Frequency	0	1	5	32	38		
	% Valid	0.0	2.6	13.2	84.2	100.0	3.82	.46
Improvement in Managerial Skills	Frequency	0	0	1	37	38		
	% Valid	0.0	0.0	2.6	97.4	100.0	3.97	.16
Other Factors	Frequency	0	0	30	8	38		
	% Valid	0.0	0.0	78.9	21.1	100.0	3.21	.41

Source: Field data

The study objective was to identify the factors that significantly motivated head teachers in Marakwet West Sub County to enroll for the KEMI Diploma in Educational Management Course. Head teachers were asked to rate how each factor motivated them to enroll for the KEMI diploma in educational Management. The factors investigated were government sponsorship, convenient mode of study, Grade or job promotion and general improvement of their managerial capacity. Head teachers had latitude to introduce other factors not contemplated in the study and rate them accordingly.

Head teachers scored the degree of motivation elicited by each factor based on a four point Likert Scale as follows: (1) Very low(insignificant), (2) Low (less significant), (3) High (moderately significant) and (4) Very High (highly significant). Table 4.7 is a summary of their responses, valid percentages, the mean response and the standard deviation for each factor.

Taken singly, each factor variedly motivated head teachers to enroll for the KEMI diploma in education management. The degree of motivation by each factor on the decision by the head teacher to enroll increased with mean rating. The motivating factor, therefore, provided an indicator and the main reason behind enrolling for the KEMI diploma in educational management.

Findings of the study indicated that majority of head teachers were motivated by the need to improve their managerial skills, followed by promotion/grade, then convenient mode of study, and lastly government sponsorship.

Figure 1 Motivation by the Government Sponsorship

Figure 2 Motivation by the Convenient Mode of Study

Figure 3 Motivation by the Need for Promotion/Grade

A large standard deviation indicated high variability in head teacher opinions on the role played by motivation by the government sponsorship, and convenient mode of study on the decision made by head teachers in Marakwet west Sub County to enroll for the KEMI diploma in educational management programme.

Figure 4 Motivation by the Need to Improve Managerial Skills

The KEMI diploma in Educational Management Open and Distance Learning (ODEL) programme for pioneer trainees was largely sponsored by the government. The head teachers in Marakwet west Sub County were beneficiaries of the sponsored trainees of the pioneer ODEL programme. The trainees paid for examination and convocation fees only. Though not specifically mentioned by the head teachers, other factors might have significantly motivated them to enroll for the KEMI Diploma in education management with a mean of 3.21 (moderately significant) and a standard deviation of 0.41. Apart from the factors contemplated in the questionnaire, there is need for further research to determine these factors.

Controlling for other motivating factors, partial correlation coefficients were generated from the ratings on the motivating factors to determine whether there was any relationship between any pair of motivating factors to jointly motivate head teachers in enrolling for the KEMI diploma in Educational management. In Table 2, GOVSPO stands for government sponsorship, MOSTUD stands for convenient mode of study, PROMO stands for promotion or grade and MGTSKIL stands for improvement in management skills.

Table 2 Partial Correlation Coefficients between Motivating Factors

	GOVSPO	MOSTUD	PROMO	MGTSKIL
GOVSPO	1.0000	.8147	.8408	.4778
	0	35	35	35
	P=.	P= .000	P= .000	P= .003
MOSTUD	-	1.0000	.8259	.5021
		0	35	35
		P=.	P= .000	P= .002
PROMO	-	-	1.0000	.6620
			0	35
MGTSKIL	-	-	-	1.0000
				0
				P= .000
(Coefficient / (D.F.) / 2-tailed Significance)				

It was, therefore, construed that, a positive linear and significant relationship existed among the factors studied in jointly motivating head teachers' decision to enroll for the KEMI diploma in Education management. However the degree of motivation jointly by government sponsorship and improvement in management skills was positive but somewhat weak.

4. Conclusion

The summary findings indicated that majority of head teachers were motivated by the need to improve their managerial skills, followed by promotion/grade, then convenient mode of study, and lastly government sponsorship.

From the findings, it was concluded that head teachers did not mind to finance their training as long as such training could have been relevant and useful in meeting their school management needs and had the capacity to guarantee their upward job mobility in form of earning higher grades and promotion.

From the above findings and on the basis of the aforementioned conclusion, it was recommended that: The KEMI and other education management training institutions should develop need based programmes that are tailored towards facilitating head teachers perform their work better, Education management programmes should have the capacity to guarantee the trainees future promotions and higher salary grades and the teacher employment agency (TSC) should recognize education management certificates and promote holders of such qualifications.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There were no competing interests.

Statement of ethical approval

Research permit was sought from the National Commission for Science, Technology & Innovation (NACOSTI). Upon being granted permission (Reference NCST/RCD/14/013/1097) the researcher visited the County Education offices where authorization was granted to visit individual schools.

Statement of informed consent

In the schools informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Ndeti AM. Influence of deputy head teachers' in-service on students' discipline in Kathiani Sub-county, Machakos County, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation).
- [2] Oyuga BA. Determinants of adoption of participatory monitoring and evaluation in management of public secondary schools in Kisumu East District, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi, Kenya).
- [3] Konyango OB. Impact of resource utilization on the performance of physics in KCSE in public secondary schools in Ugunja/Ugenya districts, Kenya. Unpublished Master of Education thesis, Kenyatta University, Kenya. 2011 Nov.
- [4] Wekhuyi SA. Influence of in-service training on public secondary school principals' management of finances and human resources in Busia County, Kenya. 2014
- [5] Sharma G. Pros and cons of different sampling techniques. International journal of applied research. 2017 Nov 26;3 (7):749-52.